

Kinetics and mechanistic investigation of *N*-bromonicotinamide oxidation of aromatic aldehydes

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Abstract : *N*-Bromonicotinamide (NBN) oxidation of aromatic aldehydes is investigated in aqueous acetic acid and perchloric acid medium over the temperature range of 313–328 K. The reaction exhibits first order dependence on [NBN] and the zero order dependence on [substrate]. The fractional order dependence of rate on $[H^+]$ suggests complex formation between NBN and H^+ . The reaction fails to induce polymerization of acrylonitrile under the experimental conditions employed. Arrhenius and activation parameters are evaluated. Effects of dielectric constant and ionic strength of the medium on the reaction rate have been studied. Oxidation products are identified. A most probable reaction mechanism is proposed and an appropriate rate law is deduced to account for the observed kinetic data.

Keywords : *N*-Bromonicotinamide, aldehydes, oxidation, kinetics, mechanism.

Introduction

N-Halogeno compounds are known to be versatile oxidizing agents¹. The kinetics of oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes by *N*-bromosuccinimide^{2,3}, chloramine-T^{4,5}, 1-chlorobenzotriazole⁶, potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) in aqueous alkaline medium catalysed by osmium tetroxide⁷, hexamethylene-tetramine-bromine⁸, quinolinium chlorochromate⁹, peroxomonosulphuric acid¹⁰, *N*-chlorosuccinimide¹¹ and *N*-chloronicotinamide¹² has been investigated by various workers. The biologically important NBN has been chosen as oxidizing agent due to the antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *Solmonella enterocolitica*, *Shigella flexeri* and *Staphylococcus aureus* at different concentrations has been reported by disc diffusion method¹³. Kinetics of oxidation of amino acids¹⁴ by NBN is reported in the literature. In the present study oxidation of benzaldehyde and substituted benzaldehydes with *N*-bromonicotinamide (NBN) has been reported.

Results and discussion

The kinetics of oxidation of aldehydes by NBN is investigated at several initial concentrations of the reactants. Under the condition $[NBN] \ll [aldehyde]$, the oxidation of aldehyde by NBN proceeds smoothly at 40 °C in aqueous acetic acid. The plot of $\log(a-x)$ against time

is found to be linear ($r = >0.99$) showing a first order dependence on [NBN]. The pseudo-first order rate constant does not change with increase in initial concentration of the oxidant. The constancy of pseudo-first order rate constant at different [substrate] at constant [NBN] indicates the reaction is zero order with respect to [substrate] and also substituents (Table 1).

Effect of $[H^+]$ is investigated by varying $[HClO_4]$ at constant $[Br^-]$. Increase in $[H^+]$ ion increased the rate constant of the reaction (Table 2). The plot of $\log k$ versus $\log [H^+]$ is linear with slope = 0.6 indicating fractional order dependence on $[HClO_4]$. Effect of $[Br^-]$ on the rate of the reaction has also been studied by increasing $[KBr]$ at constant $[HClO_4]$. Addition of KBr has no significant effect on the rate of the reaction. The reaction is conducted at different ionic strengths using $NaClO_4$ and keeping the concentrations of other reactants constant. Increase in ionic strength of the medium has no observable change on the rate of the reaction.

The increase in percentage of acetic acid in the reaction mixture decreases the rate (Table 3). Plot of $\log k$ versus $1/D$ (D is the dielectric constant of the medium) is found to be linear. Added nicotinamide has negligible effect on the rate of the reaction. The reaction mixture fails to initiate polymerization of aqueous acrylonitrile solution, indicating the absence of free radicals.

Table 1. Effect of [Aldehyde] on the reaction rate at 313 K

[NBN] = $3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, [HClO₄] = $1.0 \times 10^{-1} M$, [NaClO₄] = $1.0 \times 10^{-1} M$, Solvent = 70% Acetic acid (v/v)

$k_1 \times 10^4 s^{-1}$

[Aldehyde] $\times 10^2 M$	Benzaldehyde	<i>o</i> -Chloro- benzaldehyde	<i>m</i> -Chloro- benzaldehyde	<i>p</i> -Chloro- benzaldehyde	<i>o</i> -Nitro- benzaldehyde	<i>m</i> -Nitro- benzaldehyde	<i>p</i> -Nitro- benzaldehyde
2.0	3.15	3.18	3.20	3.11	3.25	3.27	3.23
3.0	3.14	3.21	3.22	3.13	3.22	3.24	3.22
4.0	3.15	3.19	3.20	3.12	3.23	3.25	3.19
5.0	3.12	3.17	3.21	3.12	3.24	3.26	3.20
6.0	3.16	3.21	3.23	3.13	3.23	3.27	3.19

Table 2. Effect of [HClO₄] on rate of the reaction at 313 K

[Aldehyde] = $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, [NBN] = $3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, [NaClO₄] = $1.0 \times 10^{-1} M$, Solvent = 70% Acetic acid (v/v)

$k_1 \times 10^4 s^{-1}$

[HClO ₄] <i>M</i>	Benzaldehyde	<i>o</i> -Chloro- benzaldehyde	<i>m</i> -Chloro- benzaldehyde	<i>p</i> -Chloro- benzaldehyde	<i>o</i> -Nitro- benzaldehyde	<i>m</i> -Nitro- benzaldehyde	<i>p</i> -Nitro- benzaldehyde
0.10	3.15	3.18	3.20	3.11	3.25	3.27	3.23
0.12	3.54	3.51	3.62	3.52	3.68	3.70	3.66
0.14	3.84	3.89	3.95	3.83	3.97	3.99	3.86
0.16	4.19	4.22	4.24	4.21	4.26	4.28	4.22
0.18	4.56	4.61	4.62	4.58	4.66	4.73	4.60

Table 3. Effect of solvent polarity on reaction at 313 K

[Aldehyde] = $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, [NBN] = $3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, [NaClO₄] = $1.0 \times 10^{-1} M$, [HClO₄] = $1.0 \times 10^{-1} M$

$k_1 \times 10^4 s^{-1}$

Acetic acid % (v/v)	<i>D</i>	Benzaldehyde	<i>o</i> -Chloro- benzaldehyde	<i>m</i> -Chloro- benzaldehyde	<i>p</i> -Chloro- benzaldehyde	<i>o</i> -Nitro- benzaldehyde	<i>m</i> -Nitro- benzaldehyde	<i>p</i> -Nitro- benzaldehyde
60	92.9	3.51	3.58	3.61	3.48	3.74	3.76	3.69
70	84.9	3.15	3.18	3.20	3.11	3.25	3.27	3.23
80	76.7	2.56	2.63	2.64	2.48	2.71	2.73	2.65
90	59.4	1.69	2.15	2.17	1.68	2.21	2.23	2.07

The oxidation of aldehydes is studied at different temperatures (313–328 K). Arrhenius and the activation parameters are evaluated. Arrhenius plot of $\log k_1$ versus $1/T$ is linear ($r = 0.990$). The energy of activation (E_a), enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger), free energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) and entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) are found to be $21.17 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $18.57 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $87.57 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $-220.5 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively at 313 K.

Mechanism :

Under the experimental conditions the possible oxidizing species are Br₂, HOBr, H₂OBr⁺ and NBNH⁺ in aqueous solution. The first order dependence of rate on [NBN] and the addition of nicotinamide having no effect on the rate and both indicate that HOBr may not be the reactive species¹⁵. Since there is no effect due to Br⁻ the

possibility of involvement of Br₂ is ruled out. If H₂OBr⁺ is the active oxidizing species, a retardation of rate by added nicotinamide is expected. However no such effect is noticed; hence the possibility of H₂OBr⁺ as the oxidizing species is ruled out. Since the rate of the reaction increases with increase in [HClO₄], it is assumed that NBNH⁺ is an effective oxidizing species in the present investigation and keeping the above data in consideration the following mechanism is proposed for the oxidation of seven aromatic aldehydes by NBN.

The total effective concentration of NBN is $[\text{NBN}]_t$ then

$$[\text{NBN}]_t = [\text{NBN}] + [\text{NBNH}^+] \quad (4)$$

From step (1)

$$[\text{NBN}] = [\text{NBNH}^+]/K[\text{H}^+]$$

Substituting for $[\text{NBN}]$ in (4)

$$[\text{NBN}]_t = ([\text{NBNH}^+]/K[\text{H}^+]) + [\text{NBNH}^+]$$

$$[\text{NBN}]_t = [\text{NBNH}^+]\{1 + K[\text{H}^+]/K[\text{H}^+]\}$$

$$[\text{NBNH}^+] = K[\text{NBN}]_t [\text{H}^+]/1 + K[\text{H}^+] \quad (5)$$

From the slow step (2)

$$\text{Rate} = -d[\text{NBN}]_t/dt = k_1[\text{NBNH}^+][\text{H}_2\text{O}] \quad (6)$$

Substituting for $[\text{NBNH}^+]$ from (5) in the eq. (6) the following rate law is obtained.

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{Kk_1[\text{NBN}]_t[\text{H}^+]}{1 + K[\text{H}^+]}$$

The above rate law is in agreement with the observed kinetic results that the reaction follows first order with respect to $[\text{NBN}]$ and fractional order on $[\text{H}^+]$.

Since the rate = $k'[\text{NBN}]_t$

$$k' = Kk_1[\text{H}^+]/1 + K[\text{H}^+]$$

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1 + K[\text{H}^+]}{Kk_1[\text{H}^+]}$$

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1}{Kk_1[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{1}{k'}$$

From the intercept and the slope of linear double reciprocal plot of $1/k'$ versus $1/[\text{H}^+]$ values of K and k_1 for benzaldehyde are found to be $4.71 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and $9.80 \times 10^{-4} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ($r = 0.9952$) respectively. The oxidation of alcohols and aliphatic ketones by *N*-chloro succinimide¹⁶ and *N*-bromo succinimide¹⁷ have been reported to take place through the intermediate forms of protonated species of the oxidant like NCSH^+ and NBSH^+ .

Hiremath *et al.* investigated the kinetics and mechanism oxidation of chloramphenicol by 1-chlorobenzotriazole (CBT) in acidic medium¹⁸. A first order dependence on $[\text{CBT}]$ and fractional order dependence on $[\text{H}^+]$ has been reported. It suggests that the complex $[\text{CBTH}^+]$

is the oxidizing species. A similar mechanism has been reported by Rangadurai *et al.* for the oxidation of benzyl alcohol by CBT¹⁹. The negligible effect of nicotinamide on the rate indicates that it is not involved in pre-equilibrium²⁰. The change in the ionic strength of the medium does not alter the rate, which shows that the non-ionic species are involved in the rate determining step. A slight positive dielectric constant effect on the rate supports the formation of polar complex in the rate determining step²¹. The proposed mechanism is supported by the observed value of energy of activation. The fairly high positive values of free energy of activation indicate that the transition state is highly solvated, while the high negative entropy of activation suggests the formation of compact activated complex.

Experimental

NBN was prepared²² in acetic acid (Merck) and the purity was checked iodometrically²³. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade. The solutions of the seven aromatic aldehydes were prepared in acetic acid. Kinetic runs were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions ($[\text{aldehyde}] \gg [\text{NBN}]$). Requisite amounts of aldehyde, perchloric acid, sodium perchlorate and aqueous acetic acid were taken in a jena glass reaction vessel and placed in a water thermostat maintained at the desired temperature for 30 min. The reaction was initiated by rapid addition of NBN solution and its progress was followed by estimating iodometrically the amount of unconsumed NBN at regular intervals of time.

Product analysis and stoichiometric study :

The reaction mixture containing excess of NBN over aldehyde (3 : 1) in the presence of HClO_4 and NaClO_4 were kept at the room temperature for 36 h. Estimation of unreacted NBN showed that one mole of aldehyde reacted with one mole of NBN. The overall stoichiometry of the oxidation reaction may be represented as

The corresponding acid and nicotinamide were found as the major products of oxidation and were identified by TLC analysis and melting point.

Note

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